

THE DOMESTIC VIOLENCE ACT, 2005: UPPER HAND FOR WOMEN?

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, women's social status has remained poor and worrisome. Compared to now, society's attitude towards women was less accepting earlier. Unfortunately, the women had no choice but to accept the enormity of their fate because they were the victims of dominance at the hands of their husbands and in-laws. Many accepted their fate as it was, while the others who came out to report had to step back owing to a lack of specific legal provisions and improper implementation, or they had to deal with the most severe consequences of their attempt, which at times may cost them their life. The **Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005** was passed as a step towards giving women concrete legal protection to effectively defend the rights of women who were victims of violence of any type occurring inside the family.

However, the situation as it stands now is reversed. Improvements have been made in their understanding of the rights that have been given to them. There are several drawbacks to societal change. The most notable example is women utilising the Act itself as a tool to seek vengeance. These days, women find it impossible to resist taking unfair advantage of the law because the Act tends to favour them. There are several cases, some of which have been mentioned in this article itself, where it is evident how women nowadays exploit the law to harass males, demand money and pursue personal advantage. Due to the fundamental flaws present in the Act, women have abused the law against innocent men, which is unjust in the eyes of the law. Given the act's unfairness and the frequency with which it is used to harass men, it is clear that women have gained the **upper hand** as a result of the law. Men cannot challenge the Act in any way. Furthermore, there is no proof necessary for an arrest for domestic abuse, and bail is also not available. To avoid unnecessary arrests, a

comprehensive investigation should be carried out. Diverse steps need to be taken to stop the injustice done to men.

INTRODUCTION

In Indian culture, the patriarchal system is still prevalent. It's possible to think that the abuse of women started with this setup. Women from all social backgrounds, regardless of their age, religion, caste, or status, are affected by domestic abuse. It is a violent act that only impacts the victim and her children, but it has wider implications for society as well. The Indian parliament, to protect women from abuse, passed the **Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005**. It is commonly referred to as the "**DV Act**". The Indian government along with the Ministry of Women and Child Development implemented it on **26th October 2006**. The Act introduced the term "**Domestic Violence**" in Indian law for the first time. It is a comprehensive definition that covers not just physical violence, but also other types of violence like emotional and psychological abuse. It is civil legislation intended primarily for granting protection orders rather than enforcing criminal laws. The Act was inspired by **Article 15 (2)** of the Indian Constitution, which expressly states that **the "State can make special provisions for women and children"** to realize the Right to Equality. This shows how affirmative action has been used to remedy a wrong. The legislative intent behind enacting the Domestic Violence Act was to safeguard the rights of women who are victims of domestic violence of any type occurring in the family. This act safeguards women from domestic violence inside of their own four walls. In the Act, a mechanism has been put in place by setting up the office of the Protection Officer and recognizing the role of Service Providers. To help women in distress, the government has been assigned the duty to provide various amenities like medical facilities, legal aid, and shelter homes.

The Act was passed to defend women's rights and improve their social standing, but as is well known, every coin has two sides. This act has given the woman an undue advantage, and the woman is now using it against males as a weapon to extort, manipulate, and threaten them out of selfish motives in some cases. However, the court as well as society is currently extremely concerned about the misuse and abuse of the Domestic Violence Act, 2005. To ensure that the complaint made under this regulation by a woman is not an attempt at manipulation or retaliation against a man, the complaint must be carefully reviewed. The primary objective of the Act was to protect women from abuse and violence, not to establish a civil right to sue without justifiable grounds.

The law was enacted under the social status of women then but it is no longer the same after considering current circumstances it has been overturned. The Rising understanding of the rights and benefits offered as a result of improvement in women's social position. This social change has come with certain drawbacks. Since the law is biased in favor of women, they find it irresistible to take undue advantage of the law. As rightly said **“All power corrupts and absolute power corrupts absolutely”**, women have started using the Act as a tool to harass men by filing a false complaints. **The common perception of society is that males are the abusers and women are the victims.** As a result of this impression, some women have begun abusing the act to gain advantages from their spouses and their in-laws. The most noticeable flaw of the Act is the definition itself. The term **“Domestic violence”** as defined in the act is vague. The definition of emotional and mental abuse also includes insults and jibes. It is typical for husband and wife to hold opposing views. Sometimes these disagreements result in marital disputes that weren't meant to qualify as emotional or mental abuse. However, some women make the effort to go to court even for such trivial matters. **It's also vital to remember that under the Domestic Violence Act of 2005, the victim is always a woman. A man doesn't fall under the ambit of this Act.** As the definition is ambiguous

in nature and inclined towards women, they try to misuse the Act by making their interpretation under their convenience. An example of this is the case of **VIJAY VERMA V. STATE N.C.T OF DELHI & ANR**¹. In this case, the **petitioner** filed an application under **section 12** of the **Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act** against her brother and his wife. She is a permanent resident of the USA and she was trying to claim property rights over her parental house in India, which was owned by her father and **respondent No. 2 (brother)**. She filed a petition under the Domestic Violence Act with the motive of taking shelter of “**domestic relationship**”. After taking into consideration the term “domestic relationship” and other factors, the petition proved to be not at all maintainable. This case shows how women try to wrongly use the Domestic Violence Act for their selfish motives. She was rightly denied the relief of residence in her father’s leftover property.

According to **Section 32 (2)** of the Act, the court believes that the victim's (woman's) testimony is always accurate and that no supporting evidence is required to prove that an offense has been committed. This is extremely risky for innocent males since they have no recourse against women who may make false charges at any time owing to a grudge or retribution against them. We can see a clear example of this risk in the case of **LAKHWINDER SINGH AND ORS V. STATE OF PUNJAB AND ANR**². **Chinderpal Kaur (Respondent No. 2)** applied **section 12** of the Domestic Violence Act. The marriage between **petitioner No. 1 Lakhwinder Singh** and **respondent No. 2 Chinderpal Kaur** was already dissolved with mutual consent under **Section 13-B of the Marriage Act the Hindu, 1955**. Therefore, the application filed under **section 12** of the Domestic Violence Act, after more than 2 years of divorce was not maintainable. **Respondent No. 2** falsely accused **petitioner No. 1** of committing domestic violence against her. She also claimed

¹ Vijay Verma vs. State NCT of Delhi & ANR on 13 August 2010 (Delhi High Court)

² Lakhwinder Singh & Ors. vs. State of Punjab And ANR on 18 July 2019 (Punjab-Haryana High Court)

that **petitioner No. 1** obtained divorce by false means. The court found no force in the plea of **respondent No. 2** that the said divorce was obtained by fraud means as she appeared twice before the district judge and also her statements were duly recorded. It is visible that there has been total abuse of the process of law on the part of **respondent No. 2**.

Women have recently been wreaking havoc by utilizing the act as a tool or weapon to harass and extort men by filing fake complaints against husbands and their relatives with the ulterior purpose of obtaining property and extracting money. It can be seen in the case of **SMT. GEETANJALI V. SRI B.B. ANANTHA**³ the wife falsely filed a complaint against her husband to obtain property from him. The facts of the case reveal that the wife was tortured by her husband and that she did not receive sufficient treatment; however, the case was proved false after an investigation. She fabricated and hid crucial information to torture her husband and parents-in-law, and has exploited the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act 2005 as a tool to extract unreasonable money from her husband for unjustified personal advantage.

As women are becoming more aware of the availability of their rights, they are acting cunningly. They are misusing the provisions of the Domestic Violence Act to cover up their shortcomings.

In the case of **MAJOR SINGH & ANR V. SARABJIT KAUR**⁴, the wife made a false charge against her husband because she was having an extramarital affair. She tried to scare her spouse, but he filed for divorce.

The Punjab High Court found that the Domestic Violence Act is being abused to intimidate the spouse, their family, and distant relatives and that this phenomenon has now been called "**legal terrorism**".

The court stated that one of the most prominent drawbacks of the Act is that it lends itself to such careless misapplication that women find it difficult to resist

³ Smt. Geetanjali vs. Sri B. M. Anantha on 27 March 2018 (Bangalore District Court)

⁴ Major Singh & ANR vs. Sarabjit Kaur on 6 September 2018 (Punjab-Haryana High Court)

the desire to teach a lesson to their male relatives and file frivolous and false complaints. This may be seen in the case of **BAWINDER VERMA V. RICHA SHARMA**⁵, where the Punjab High Court passed a judgment stating that the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, contains inherent weaknesses that attract women to abuse its provisions against men.

Drawbacks are present in various sections of this Act. Considering **section 18** of this Act, the magistrate may take steps to safeguard women from any future acts of violence that are likely to occur. This means that the woman has an upper hand in terms of protection, and the person against whom they have complained can be penalized even if haven't performed any act of violence and there is merely a chance of violence occurring in the future.

Monetary relief is the most prominent form of protection that provides wings to women's evil ambitions. Previously, the actual reason why women never raised their voices against their sufferings was that they were monetarily reliant on their spouses; now, the situation is no longer the same. Women, too, are educated and economically self-sufficient, and are sometimes viewed as having more income than their male counterparts.

Those who are monetarily independent also harass their husbands by requesting monetary compensation under **section 20 (1)** of legislation. Women get monetary relief when the court decides to give compensation to the victim for damages for injuries. In such cases, compensation and order are issued.

Women have an advantage over men when it comes to custody orders as, under **section 21** of the domestic violence act, the aggrieved party (a woman) or the person who applied on her behalf is given custody of the child or children. If necessary, plans are established for the respondent to visit the child or children. However, men lose out when it comes to visitation rights since the magistrate

⁵ Balwinder Verma vs. Richa Sharma on 10 July 2018 (Punjab-Haryana High Court)

may refuse to permit such visits if he or she believes that the respondent's visits will harm the child or children.

Many women experience sexual harassment and marital rape, but if women consistently reported crimes that never happened, such women (victims) may lose the spotlight. The crucial imbalance in society is caused not only by law but also by its improper implementation. The Act is discriminative, which is evident in several sections of the Act, which encourages women to utilize it to harass men. The main motive of women-related special laws is misapplied, and as a result, the husband suffers for no fault of his own.

THE CONCLUSION

Women are now superior to men according to the Act. All of us, regardless of caste, creed, gender, etc., are granted equal rights under our Constitution. Consequently, both men and women should have equal protection under the law. The following measures should receive special attention to eliminate biases:--

1. The Domestic Violence Act needs to include the word "**Male.**" There will be less misuse as a result.
2. Men shouldn't feel threatened by their spouses' cautions. The ability to complain about their wives should likewise be granted to them.
3. After the victim filed her complaint, the police should conduct a thorough investigation.
4. Domestic violence is a crime that is not subject to bail and for which an arrest need not be supported by evidence, so a thorough investigation should be conducted.

Moreover, determining what constitutes domestic abuse punishable under this Act is also necessary to make the law more useful. It is blatant injustice to innocent people when they are threatened by the law even though they have not committed any offense.

It is undoubtedly true that some strict measures are required to keep a check on men, but this needed to be achieved not by adding more and more laws, but via efficient execution of the already existing legal framework. There are actual instances of women who are oppressed by their spouses and in-laws and imprisoned in violent marriages and the harsh domestic environment. Due to a few fake cases, all legitimate cases lose their gravity as being real and authentic, and occasionally they are questioned.

The act's goal is to protect women from domestic violence, not to give them an advantage over males by allowing them to utilize its provisions to harass men. Due to the Act's discriminative and basic inadequacies, it can be said that women have an upper hand. Women seek vengeance by using the very law that was intended to protect them.

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